

A secure and trustworthy framework for field device measurements by means of smart contracts

Alessandro Rossi¹[0009-0007-1777-6701] and Lorenzo Cristofori¹[0009-0001-0172-4508] and José L. Hernández²[0000-0002-7621-2937]

¹ Engineering Ingegneria Informatica S.p.A., Digital Twin and IoT Solutions, Rome, Italy

² Fundación CARTIF, 47151 Boecillo (Valladolid), Spain

alessandro.rossi@eng.it; Lorenzo.Cristofori@eng.it;
joshier@cartif.es

Abstract. The current trend in building-sector approaches focuses on energy management and local energy communities. These aspects rely heavily on data collected from sensor networks. However, data acquisition typically depends on communication networks, which introduces inherent risks of data manipulation. To address these risks, blockchain-based procedures can enhance trust, reliability, and security in data transmission.

This work presents a secure and trustworthy framework built on smart contract technologies. The framework is designed to provide a proof-of-existence mechanism for data monitoring. A real test scenario is used as a proof of concept, employing actual data to demonstrate how the smart contract increases confidence by ensuring data coherence.

Keywords: Data notarization, Data integrity, Data coherence, Proof of Existence, Real Time Monitoring.

1 Introduction

Blockchain technology is increasingly making its mark in the energy sector, revolutionizing the way energy is generated, distributed, and consumed. At its core, blockchain is a decentralized and distributed ledger that enables secure, transparent, and tamper-resistant recording of transactions. In the energy field, this technology introduces a new paradigm by enhancing efficiency, traceability, and trust in energy-related processes [1]. One of the key applications is in the realm of peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading, allowing consumers with renewable energy sources, such as solar panels, to directly sell excess energy to nearby consumers without the need for intermediaries [2]. This not only promotes a more sustainable and decentralized energy ecosystem but also creates opportunities for individuals to actively participate in the energy market.

In addition to P2P trading, blockchain facilitates the creation of smart grids or microgrids [3], which are intelligent and self-regulating energy distribution networks. Through the integration of blockchain, smart grids can autonomously manage and optimize the flow of energy, ensuring a more reliable and resilient energy infrastructure.

The transparent and decentralized nature of blockchain also enhances the accuracy and security of energy data management. From monitoring energy production and consumption to tracking carbon emissions, blockchain provides a tamper-proof record that stakeholders can trust [4].

Within the energy monitoring context, using blockchain for data notarization involves leveraging the decentralized and tamper-resistant nature of blockchain technology to provide a secure and verifiable way of timestamping and authenticating data. Data notarization involves the process of proving the existence, integrity, and timestamp of a specific set of data at a particular point in time [5]. The main benefit of this service is the increased confidence in the decision-making process by the creation of audit-proof applications.

In contrast with traditional notarization system, where a central authority validates and timestamps documents, in a blockchain-based system, this role is distributed across a network of nodes, making it more resilient to tampering or single points of failure. It represents a trustworthy framework to ensure secure, immutable and pseudo-anonymized data collection at field level [6]. This data notarization procedure is split into multiple steps: Data submission (either users or data ingestion tools submit monitoring data for notarization); Hashing (gathered data is converted into a cryptographic hash, which is a fixed-size string of characters unique to the data); Transaction creation (a blockchain transaction is created with the hashed data and timestamp); Consensus (network of nodes consensus on the validity of the transaction); Verification (integrity and timestamp of the data by comparing the store hash with the original data).

Blockchain-based data notarization provides a set of benefits. This service is tamper-resistance, immutability ensures that once data is notarized, it cannot be altered or deleted. It also assures decentralization, thanks to the distributed nature of blockchain eliminates the need for a central authority, reducing the risk of manipulation or fraud. Transparency allows users to independently verify the notarization process and timestamps. Cost-efficiency, compared to traditional notarization methods, can potentially reduce cost by eliminating the need for intermediaries.

According to the features and benefits that blockchain-based data notarization, this work presents a practical case demonstrated within the DigiBUILD project [7], whose aim is to transform the current silo approach in the building energy management into a digital and smart approach. A blockchain layer is added within the software architecture to provide security and privacy in the collection and historicization of data acquired from sensors. Moreover, a smart contract is also developed to implement Proof of Existence (PoE) algorithm, which is validated in a blockchain test network deployed at the VEOLIA's facilities, composed of three nodes.

The work is structured as follows. A state of the art on security and privacy techniques using blockchain with a focus on the energy domain is presented in Section 2. The software architecture where the blockchain layer is placed is described in Section 3, including the smart contract developed for the PoE algorithm. Section 4 provides the insights in a real scenario to test the applicability of the smart contracts. Finally, the conclusions of this work are reported in Section 5.

2 State of the art

Since the birth of the first blockchain, conceptualized by Satoshi Nakamoto [8], many different types of implementations have emerged. One of the most impactful ones has been Ethereum [9], which enabled the spread of decentralized applications and the consolidation of different types of consensus mechanism such as the Proof of Work (PoW) [10], the Proof of Stake (PoS) [10], and the Proof of Authority (PoA).

The blockchain technology can be used to store data ensuring immutability, security, and transparency. A blockchain is a decentralized ledger that stores transactions across a network of computers and so, in contrast to traditional Databases, there is not a single authority able to alter or delete the data. Each block of the chain contains a cryptographic hash of the previous block, creating a chronological and immutable record of all transactions.

Since each node in the network holds a copy of the ledger, the risk of single points of failure is eliminated and the risk of data manipulation or censorship reduced, making the network resilient to hacking or data loss.

For all these reasons, the blockchain technology is particularly suitable for ensuring integrity and trustworthiness of stored information.

In particular, the Ethereum blockchain enables the use of smart contracts, self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement directly written into code. These contracts are executed on the Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) [11], a Turing-complete runtime environment that allows for the execution of code on the blockchain. The nature of the blockchain and the expressiveness of the programming language allow for immutable and transparent transaction execution, enhancing security and eliminating the need for trust in intermediaries. For these reasons Ethereum and smart contracts can be used in many different use cases. One of these is the notarization of information, i.e., the registration of data (or footprint of data, for privacy reasons) for its verification in a trusted way. In traditional applications, notarization is granted by trusted centralized authorities. Blockchain technology allows to remove this need, allowing trusted registration and verification in a decentralized and transparent way.

In literature, many types of notarization tools and approaches that use blockchain as base infrastructure can be found. In [12], the authors provide a collection of tools available online for notarization of documents and for antiplagiarism checking, thus showing an approach that integrates the two functionalities by allowing notarization only following a successful anti-plagiarism check.

The support of the usage of a blockchain for the notarization of documents can be found in applications of even very different domains. For example, [13] proposes an approach in which queries made to databases containing biomedical evidence and the corresponding result are notarized inside a blockchain using smart contracts ensuring the integrity and non-reputation of the data retrieved.

Another example of the applicability of these notarization techniques to different domains is the work reported in [14]. In this work, the authors describe a blockchain-based system for the notarization of water quality data registered from sensing devices. The notarization is made once per day by a notarization oracle or can be done from an operator manually. The software architecture presented in this paper was used for

notarization of data streams and applied to a proof of concept in the energy field, as reported in [6].

2.1 Contribution of this work

The main contribution of this work is the realization and the application in a real case of a software architecture that offers a complete notarization tool, using two smart contracts, by exploiting the capabilities offered by the blockchain, and in particular by Ethereum. The developed solution offers two different methods of notarization, the first for data streams, by means of the Monitoring Data Notarization (MDN) smart contract and the second for single documents of any kind, asynchronously, by means of the Proof of Existence (PoE) smart contract.

The PoE offers the functionality of storing data in an immutable manner, calculating the hash of the document to be notarized or registering directly the hash calculated off-chain. It is then possible to verify that a document has been notarized by its content or hash, using the corresponding PoE method. For privacy reasons, the second way is generally preferable, even if in some use cases the first one is acceptable and easier to implement (e.g., when data to be notarized are not sensitive and can be published and notarized directly, without any drawback).

3 Software architecture

3.1 The security and privacy layer

The work presented in this paper has been produced in the framework of the DigiBUILD project, and in particular for the implementation of its security and privacy layer. Within the data management and governance architecture, this layer is transversal to the data acquisition, storage and sharing, as illustrated in Fig. 1. This layer includes the use of two smart contracts for notarization and historicization of information acquired by the monitoring systems part of the same project. Data flow and processing are depicted in Fig. 2.

The security and privacy layer allows the data notarization and certification of given documents or a set of data measures calculating a footprint stored into the blockchain. Calculating and storing a footprint is done for:

- Limit the size of the data to be stored into the blockchain.
- Ensure the privacy of the referenced data.

Whereas the blockchain is used to store encrypted data, the security layer envisages an 'off-chain' database for storing unencrypted data. In case of monitoring data, the 'off-chain' storage functionality is implemented through Time Series Database (TSDB) [15].

The two main components of the security and privacy layers are real-time monitoring (RTM) via the Monitoring Data Notarization (MDN) smart contract and Proof of Existence (PoE) via the homonym smart contract.

Fig. 1. DigiBUILD data management architecture with focus on the privacy & security layer

Fig. 2. Conceptual approach for the Smart Contracts developed, RMT and PoE cases.

The two smart contracts perform notarization of data but in two different ways. The MDN smart contract performs the notarization of streams of data divided in bulk of a fixed time window (more information about that and a real demonstration can be found in [6]), while the PoE smart contract perform notarization of single documents and will describe in details in the following section.

3.2 Smart contracts

Monitoring Data Notarization (MDN). The monitoring data notarization smart contract can be used to notarized data in real time without having to perform a transaction in the blockchain for each piece of data recorded by the sensors, which are generally registered at too high a rate to be managed directly with the blockchain. For this reason, the hash of the data is generated from a bulk of data retrieved from an off-chain database that is grouped into sets of data of exactly the same duration (e.g., every 15 minutes) and notarized in the blockchain with the timestamp reference. More information on the MDN smart contract and an example of its usage can be found in [6].

Proof of Existence (PoE). The Proof of Existence smart contract, unlike the MDN, can be used for the notarization of single documents of any type, asynchronously and without a fixed rate. To provide a tool as generic as possible the PoE smart contract includes the following 5 main methods and 1 utility function:

- **certify:** calculate the hash of a document and register its proof of existence through its content.
- **check:** calculate the hash of a document and prove its existence through its content.
- **getProof:** get the proof of the document associated with a notarized hash.
- **notarize:** register the proof of existence of a document through its hash.
- **verify:** prove the existence of a document through its hash.
- **digest:** calculate the proof of a document as the SHA-3 hash of its content.

Each document is notarized by means of its hash. The implemented methods directly accept the hash of the document calculated off-chain, but there are also two methods which accepts the content of the document for the calculation of the hash on chain. If internally calculated, the proof of the document is computed as the hash of its contents using the SHA3 hash algorithm [16].

Along its hash, the proof of existence of each document includes metadata such as the timestamp of the notarization and an optional description field, which can be used to store unencrypted publicly available information about the document and the proof itself. In Fig. 3 the dynamic view of the PoE is depicted.

Initially, the PoE subscribes to the FIWARE Context Broker for notarization requests. When the Data Producer sends a notarization request, the FIWARE Context Broker, which can be used to authenticate devices through Keyrock and Wilma PEP Proxy, notifies the PoE to create the hash and notarize it, inserting the corresponding transaction in the next block mined. Once the transaction is finished and a new block

has been mined, the proof of the notarization, containing the notarized hash, the timestamp and the block number containing the corresponding transaction, is captured by the PoE and sent back to the Data Producer.

After that, the Data Producer (or any other actor having access to the data and/or the hash) can verify the original data, asking the PoE to recalculate the hash on the same data, and verify if it is the same of the one already notarized into the blockchain.

Fig. 3. Sequence Diagram for the PoE.

4 Real case scenario

As mentioned earlier, the security framework, rooted in blockchain smart contracts, supports dynamic data ingestion mechanisms. Specifically, it leverages RTM and PoE concepts to ensure consistency by comparing hashes, thereby detecting communication errors or data manipulation in the data acquisition process.

To showcase the feasibility of the algorithms, a real testing network has been used, employing the VEOLIA pilot (demonstrator). This pilot comprises a district heating network with twenty substations and the boiler room. In this setup, nodes based on Okdo Rock boards were deployed in the boiler room and two substations, as illustrated in Fig. 4. The blockchain network is implemented using Hyperledger Besu, with the EthSigner wallet serving as the endpoint for access from the dApps (i.e., PoE and RTM). The main features of the boards are:

- Rockchip RK3588 SoC.

- Octa-core processor with Arm® DynamIQ™ Quad Cortex® A76, Quad Cortex® A55 CPU, and Arm Mali™ G610MC4 GPU.
- 8GB 64-bit RAM and eMMC socket.

Fig. 4. VEOLIA blockchain network configuration with the three nodes for the deployment of the RTM and PoE Smart Contracts.

To achieve this, the methodology shown in Fig. 5 has been applied. Initially, real data was extracted from monitoring datasets and subsequently filtered and cleaned. In the second step, the hash of the data sample was calculated before transmitting the transaction for data certification. Finally, the verification function is executed to validate the hash upon receiving the data at the endpoint.

Fig. 5. Consistency check procedure applied from the Smart Contracts

To ensure efficient hashing without overwhelming string size, only the first row of the read data is utilized. The data to be certified is as follows:

```

    ('Location', 'EDEN1D - M209026 - POBLADO DE FASA - ARCO LADRILLO
    95') ('ID', 49150) ('Variable', 'ENERGIA CONTADOR 1° CALEFACC (15
    minutes)') ('Timestamp', '2023-03-01 00:15:00.000') ('Value',
    1164.41)
  
```

The chosen cryptographic algorithm is SHA256, resulting in the hash:

```

    b"\xd5\x82\xd5\xeaS\xc1\xb8|\x8c\xd7\xba/\x03I\xc8w\x17>\x98B
    \x16\x91\x87\xac\xfd\x14\x1bP'a
  
```

After sending the dataset, the blockchain network certifies the data, generating the following log:

```

    AttributeDict({'args': AttributeDict({'': AttributeDict({'de-
    scription': 'data from VEOLIA', 'provider':
  
```

```
'0xb8f356ab125212CCd7017D8766B0463B531bA137',      'timestamp':  
1700053800}})), 'event': 'Notarized', 'logIndex': 0, 'transac-  
tionIndex': 0, 'transactionHash':  
HexBytes('0x0310cf7829b8a11414ce1306acf6fe0dd8acd3908a13a9b2ce2  
5bab40436c11'), 'address':  
'0x8a442905884c6a62938a77600aAeC7c9a073AAD7', 'blockHash':  
HexBytes('0x8548aabb4683617de8c49551b9f3a49ed36c94780a6baeea1f2d  
10cc9cd6717e'), 'blockNumber': 3641})
```

The notarization of the data is evident from the log, indicating that the transaction is available in block #3641 of the blockchain network. The log also includes the node's address that signed the transaction and the transaction hash for traceability. This process occurs at the source (on the pilot side), enabling the verification of data coherence and consistency at the destination side. Consequently, it allows the detection of communication issues that may corrupt data, ensuring that the data read in the pilot and stored in the data lake remains unchanged during the communication process.

5 Conclusions

In this paper, a blockchain-based solution for decentralized security and privacy has been presented, together with an initial real-case implementation scenario. The core of the tool consists of two smart contracts, the PoE and the MDN, each characterized by a different data-certification periodicity. These smart contracts have been evaluated within the real-case scenario and deployed accordingly.

This work illustrates and demonstrates how blockchain technology can be used to ensure data integrity and coherence throughout the data acquisition and transfer process. Security and privacy are guaranteed on-chain through the use of anonymized hashes. The potential applications of this tool extend across multiple domains, not only the energy sector. Further developments of the tool and its use in various contexts will be addressed in future work.

Acknowledgments. All the developed solution, its design and implementation, have been conducted within the EU co-funded Project called “DigiBUILD”, Grant Agreement No. 101069658. Therefore, authors would like to thank both the European Commission for funding the project, as well as the partners, especially VEOLIA, for the support provided.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

- [1] L. Angelo, F. Gianluca, S. Fred e P. Estathios, *Distributed Power Generation in Europe: Technical Issues for Further Integration*, Luxembourg (Luxembourg): OPOCE, 2008.
- [2] S. Gutiérrez, J. Hernandez, A. Navarro e R. Viruega, «Energy Trading Between Prosumers Based on Blockchain Technology,» 2022, pp. 24-33.
- [3] D. Pudjianto, C. Ramsay e G. Strbac, «Microgrids and virtual power plants: Concepts to support the integration of distributed energy resources,» *Proceedings of the Institution of Mechanical Engineers, Part A: Journal of Power and Energy*, vol. 222, pp. 731-741, 2008.
- [4] A. Ahmed, S. Abdullah, M. Bukhsh, I. Ahmad e Z. Mushtaq, «An Energy-Efficient Data Aggregation Mechanism for IoT Secured by Blockchain,» *IEEE Access*, vol. 10, pp. 11404-11419, 2022.
- [5] C. Eyhoff e W. Prinz, «Using the Blockchain as Notary Service for a Local Energy Market,» in *2022 IEEE 7th International Energy Conference (ENERGYCON)*, 2022.
- [6] A. Rossi, A. Natalini, L. Cristofori e M. Mammina, «A tool for the data notarization with the Blockchain to ensure security and privacy,» in *2023 IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Living Environment (MetroLivEnv)*, 2023.
- [7] GA#101069658, «DigiBUILD Project,» [Online]. Available: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101069658>.
- [8] S. Nakamoto, «Bitcoin whitepaper,» URL: <https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf> (: 17.07. 2019), 2008.
- [9] V. Buterin e others, «Ethereum white paper,» *GitHub repository*, vol. 1, p. 22–23, 2013.
- [10] D. Mingxiao, M. Xiaofeng, Z. Zhe, W. Xiangwei e C. Qijun, «A review on consensus algorithm of blockchain,» in *2017 IEEE international conference on systems, man, and cybernetics (SMC)*, 2017.
- [11] G. Wood e others, «Ethereum: A secure decentralised generalised transaction ledger,» *Ethereum project yellow paper*, vol. 151, p. 1–32, 2014.
- [12] T. Palmisano, V. N. Convertini, L. Sarcinella, L. Gabriele e M. Bonifazi, «Notarization and Anti-Plagiarism: A New Blockchain Approach,» *Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, 2022.
- [13] A.-S. Kleinaki, P. Mytis-Gkometh, G. Drosatos, P. S. Efraimidis e E. Kaldoudi, «A Blockchain-Based Notarization Service for Biomedical Knowledge Retrieval,» *Computational and Structural Biotechnology Journal*, vol. 16, pp. 288-297, 2018.
- [14] M. Cabras, M. I. Lunesu, A. Pinna e G. Fenu, «A Notarization System for Water Quality Parameters,» in *2023 IEEE/ACM 6th International Workshop on Emerging Trends in Software Engineering for Blockchain (WETSEB)*, 2023.

- [15] J. L. Hernández, S. Martín, V. Marinakis e I. de Miguel, «From silos to open, federated and enriched Data Lakes for smart building data management,» in *IEEE International Workshop on Metrology for Living Environment (MetroLivEnv)*, Milano, 2023.
- [16] G. Bertoni, J. Daemen, M. Peeters e G. Van Assche, «Keccak,» in *Advances in Cryptology – EUROCRYPT 2013*, Berlin, 2013.